

MULTI-MEDIA COMPETENCE AS A COMPONENT OF FUTURE TEACHER TRAINING OF THE GERMAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Many works have already been devoted to the problems of using new information technologies for educational purposes, where a paradigm shift in education is proposed, the development of a personality-oriented approach to education within the framework of philosophy, psychology and pedagogy, and cognitive-psychological theories and the theory of constructivism are considered as a theoretical basis.*

Keywords: *reflection, analysis, multimedia competence, multimedia; interactivity; hyper textuality, interactive learning.*

Today, the main psychological theories on which foreign language teaching using new technologies is based are cognitive psychology and the theory of constructivism. The first approach is to model human cognitive processes using a computer and use this model to solve the problem of optimal control of the learning process.

The second approach, first proposed by Glazerfeld, Forster, connects the entire learning process directly with the theory of constructivism.

Many works have already been devoted to the problems of using new information technologies for educational purposes, where a paradigm shift in education is proposed, the development of a personality-oriented approach to education within the framework of philosophy, psychology and pedagogy, and cognitive-psychological theories and the theory of constructivism are considered as a theoretical basis.

Based on the results of research in the field of cognitive psychology related to the situation of learning with the help of Internet technologies, scientists define ideas about the processes of understanding in the multimedia working environment of the educational process. We are talking about how a person chooses meaningful information from the flow of information, which he understands based on his previous knowledge. At the same time, it is important that a person is able to decompose information into small specific parts, but he can also combine small portions of information into large groups.

But it should be noted that the introduction of the Internet into the process of teaching foreign languages has both advantages and disadvantages. So, what cannot give the process of learning foreign languages on the Internet? It should be noted that learning on the Internet does not replace real face-to-face communication, and therefore for a long time the normal traditional educational situation in the classroom will remain as the basis for teaching foreign languages, because we proceed from the fact that today, Internet communication is written communication. This fact suggests that reading and writing are extremely important skills needed to work in the www network. This means that in the future, written contact communication is "real" to enrich

foreign language classes. In this sense, learning using the Internet is authentic, because it represents real communication with a "stranger" in real time.

In the methodological literature, the concept of multimedia is defined as: a means of accumulating information; a means of encoding information; a means of transmitting information; a means of transporting information; a means of reproducing information; a means of perceiving information. Such a context is most adequate for considering the problems of self-organization of the www network, the Internet. From this point of view, the problem of cognition of the Internet is the problem of cognition of new forms of dialogue and communication, when new sign-semantic spaces of communication are born, when not text, but hypertext and context are read; when new methods of strategy and skills appear, because new schemes of understanding and assimilation of knowledge related to the visual series, image, shape, color are born.

In the scientific literature, the specifics of the Internet are represented by the following three aspects: multimedia; interactivity; hyper textuality.

Let's analyze the first aspect:

Multimedia is a "key technology" of the information space, an open information world, presented in the form of: portals, search engines, catalogs, websites, electronic dictionaries, encyclopedias, virtual universities. Internet materials are constructed as structures where "free reception of multimedia information through the Kerres network" takes place [1].

The most important feature of multimedia is that they cover most types of cultures in their field in all their diversity. All manifestations of culture are connected in this digital universe, which connects past, present and future manifestations of communicative thought in a giant historical super text.

The second value of the Internet, its second aspect is interactivity. E-mail, chat, and video conferencing services open up opportunities for direct authentic communication between speakers of the same language and the language being studied, with "native speakers". These opportunities in their diversity, transmission speed, special independence, content are not comparable with traditional forms of work. The role of the Internet for intercultural communication and understanding in this case is demonstrated by examples of bilingual e-mail tandems. Interactivity means the ability to interact or be in the mode of conversation, dialogue with someone (for example, with a computer or an interlocutor) [5].

The third aspect of the Internet is hypertext, where hypertext is the structure of the Internet. Hypertext is an associative connection of information parts through servers or links that allow access to the point of connection with texts. Along with multimedia offers, there is also a "jump-like" connection from one information center to another, where it is possible to view network materials. The result of one's own work when using multimedia causes certain positive emotions that generate additional motivation for studying.

Multimedia competence is the ability to use Internet technologies in the process of mastering a foreign language, i.e. to learn a language and teach it in a multimedia, interactive and hypertextual environment.

This ability is based on the skills of self-organization of the cognitive process, as a process of speech and writing reproduction, as a process taking place inside the human brain and outside (in the space of multimedia networks), as a process of synergetic and constructivist interaction of the brain with all obvious and non-obvious objects [3].

Multimedia competence includes three components: the first component of multimedia competence - multimedia implies the possession of the following models of work in the www network:

- a model for using virtual environments (virtual projects, e-mail tandems, games);
- a model for organizing your own information (its receipt, verification, evaluation, use of electronic encyclopedias and dictionaries);
- a model of creativity., for example, the creation of animations, films, electronic newspapers and video exhibitions using an electronic camera);
- a model of communication, as communication between remote communicants, which is less connected with speaking, word and sound, but is carried out through an image, form, color with a simplified communication language.

The web pages of these sites contain information about German politics, its culture, literature, history, language, etc. When viewing these links, their hyperlinks are found when you can switch from one link to another that is of interest to the trainees. Internet addresses for "Deutsch als Fremdsprache (DaF)" will give the future teacher an initial orientation on the Internet. Links are updated and expanded all the time due to new offers. Recommended addresses are divided into web pages containing the following materials, for example:

1) "Classics of German Literature" (proposal of the Goethe Institute):
<http://www.goethe.de/Z/dimidex.htm/>

2) instructions, recommendations for German language learners;
<http://www.goeüte.de/Z/demidex/htm/>

3) special selection of materials for German language teachers:
<http://www.goeibe.de/r/daf/dservueb.htm>

4) An interactive overview of DaF on the Internet is offered on the websites:
<http://www.stud.uni-muenchen.de/~fariborz.dadkhah-j.azi>

5) collections of exercises: <http://ibm.zhrz.uni-bonn.de/~usa000/idex.html>

6) language games:<http://texthaus.cot/7>) materials on country studies:
<http://www.schulweb.de> <http://www.ids.mannheim.de/quellen/kunde/htm/> <http://www.ualberta.ca/~german/lehrer/htm/> - It should be noted that all addresses are constantly updated

b) e-mail (e-mail): e-mail (e-mail) connects users via the Internet, makes it possible to quickly send written texts around the world. Messages are written in everyday language, slang, which is very interesting for most students. An e-mail letter is usually written spontaneously, and - this spontaneity is comparable to oral speech.

As can be seen from the materials obtained from the www network, the Internet today is the best means of transporting information for the following reasons: because it provides instant and complete access to the entire volume of world knowledge; because it provides transportation not just information, but the delivery of such information, which includes information mediated by a powerful search center, which frees the recipient of this information from the need to plan and carry out multi-stage work on obtaining certain knowledge, information.

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